

Mathematical Modeling for Theologians

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- **Week 1: Introduction - What is a Model?**
 - Discussion on what mathematical modeling is, and why abstracting reality through equations matters (e.g. for use in computer simulations). Discussion of parallels in law and scripture.
- **Week 2: Set Theory as Language of Belonging**
 - Sets, subsets, intersections as a metaphor for identity and the differences between people, and diversity/inclusivity as a means for growing in love. For example, even Christianity encourages interfaith dialogue (“*Test everything, hold fast what is good*” - 1 Thessalonians 5:21)
- **Week 3: Functions and Relations**
 - Mapping inputs to outputs through functions. “Laws” of cause and effect. Discussion on “karma” in eastern religions, “*an eye for an eye*”, “*sowing and reaping*”, etc. Discussion on limitations of functions (such as due to experimental data/noise/interference) mirroring limitations of our understanding of moral processes.
- **Week 4: Optimization**
 - Min/max problems, constraints, trade-offs. Biblical parallels: “the greatest commandment,” choosing harm reduction when the most loving action feels improbable. Maybe a philosophical discussion on the trolley problem, connection to jurisprudence, etc.
- **Week 5: Calculus/Differential Equations**
 - Discrete vs continuous functions, Change over time, equilibrium, stability. Sin, repentance, sanctification as dynamic processes. Discussion on allegory vs literal interpretation (e.g. scientifically proven evolution abstracted in the Genesis creation story)
- **Week 6: Boundary Conditions and Systems Thinking**
 - How context shapes outcomes – different boundary conditions lead to completely different outcomes. Use different solutions of the Schrodinger Equation in quantum

mechanics to demonstrate this. Then, discussion on biblical abstractions (e.g. Sabbath, rituals, etc.) as boundary conditions.

- **Week 7: Texts as Models**

- Proverbs, parables as compressed wisdom - abstraction vs. literalism. Discuss proverbs from other cultures (e.g. Ifá verses from the Yoruba religion) and how each culture's proverbs point to the foundational principle of love (Romans 2:14-15)

- **Week 8: Faith as Developed Trust**

- Probability/statistics and confidence intervals, use of simulations in engineering as a parallel to how faith can somehow depend on probability. Discussion of placebo vs faith in From Heat to the Heart, contrasting Mark 10:52 "*your faith has made you well*" with Mark 6:5 (Christ "unable" to do miracles due to a lack of faith).

- **Week 9: Student Projects / Final Presentations**

- Each student presents a text (biblical, or other religion/moral/ethical thought) as an "abstraction model," and discussing what reality it simplifies and reveals.

LEARNING OUTCOMES

By the end of this course, students will be able to:

- **Identify abstraction in mathematical models** (e.g., sets, optimization, differential equations) and explain their conceptual significance without relying on technical computation.
- **Draw parallels between mathematical abstraction and theological texts**, recognizing how both function as simplified frameworks that reveal deeper realities.
- **Critically analyze biblical texts and other wisdom traditions** (e.g., parables, proverbs, diasporic narratives) as forms of modeling, asking what dimensions of experience they simplify, highlight, or constrain.
- **Apply systems thinking to theological and ethical questions**, showing how boundary conditions, equilibrium, and optimization concepts illuminate themes like law, faith, and sanctification.
- **Develop and present an original project that interprets a text** (biblical, diasporic, or other cultural/religious source) as an abstraction model, articulating both its limits and its theological insight.

P.S. I think a more mathematics-heavy analog titled "**Theology for Mathematicians**" would be cool too!!